

Sustainable Practices in Turnkey Cassava Processing: Techno-Economic Analysis

Ohwofadjeke, P. O^{1*}., Tulagha, I²., Udo, A. E³., Stephen, L. U⁴., Osuagwu, C. O⁵., Ogbonna, O. S¹., Okoye, N. M⁶ and Adigio, E. M⁷.

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo. P.M.B. 1038 Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria.

²Department of Agricultural and Environmental Engineering, Faculty of Engineering. Niger Delta University. Wilberforce Island. Bayelsa State.

³Department of Marine Engineering, Akwa Ibom State, University. Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

⁴Department of Civil Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental sciences. Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria.

⁵Department of Agricultural Economics. University of Agriculture and Environmental Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria.

⁶Department of Agriculture and Biosystems Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria.

⁷Department of Mechanical Engineering, Nigeria Maritime University (NMU), Okerenkoko, Delta State, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: paul.ohwofadjeke@uaes.edu.ng

Received: October 23, 2023; Accepted: December 10, 2023 ; Published: March 17, 2024

Doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10827962

Abstract: This paper assessed the economic, environmental impact, financial and technical requirements for establishment and sustainable management of modern cassava processing business, aimed at producing high-quality cassava derivatives for various markets and industrial applications. The methodology applied considered seven different models of cassava processing equipment. Each of these designs (models/lines) processes raw cassava tubers into specific derivatives like: Garri (white or oiled/yellow); Cassava starch; Cassava flour and bio-ethanol respectively. The models were designated as: “A”, “B”, “C”, “D”, “E”, “F” and “G”. Cost data were extracted from “bill of engineering measurement and evaluation” of the different design which constituted the primary source of data for the research. Analysis of collected data was carried out using payback period method and breakeven point for respective cassava processing equipment models. Results of analysis proved that model “F” had the shortest recovery period of ten months when used to process/produce red (oiled) garri and smallest breakeven point of 55,966 units thereby making it more attractive to potential investors. The general rule of thumb for business feasibility assessment considers business models with less than three years capital recovery period (payback period) to be viable. In order to internalize the economy of scale in cassava processing, the following recommendations were proposed by the authors: (1) provision of access road to the factory location/site to ease material haulage; and provision of security/surveillance cameras at strategic points within the factory. The findings and recommendations of this paper will be beneficial to potential investors and cassava farmers globally.

Keywords: Stock management; internalize; garri; geo-fencing; and cassava derivatives

Introduction

Cassava production may be said to have originated from the northeastern part of Brazil/Paraguay to Mexico and Guatemala in more than 4,000 years ago (Otegunrin, and Sawicka, 2019). It is believed that cassava was introduced to western part of Africa in 1588 through Portuguese merchants and first cultivated in Gulf of Guinea and the Congo Basin. The cultivation later spread to Madagascar and other eastern part of Africa (Otegunrin, and Sawicka, 2019). Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) is an important staple tropical root crop recognized as a 21st century crop mostly for smallholder farmers. Its starchy roots are a major source of dietary energy for more than 500 million people globally (Droppelmann, *et al.*,2018). Cassava is known to be the highest producer of carbohydrates among staple crops (Droppelmann, *et al.*,2018; Methil, *et al.*, 2021).

Cassava processing business is a rudimentary industry although large, it is underdeveloped, inefficient and uncompetitive in the global arena, a consequence of high ex-factory prices (Beeching, *et al.*,1993). Cassava roots have a high moisture content at harvest (typically 60–75% wet basis), which makes it highly perishable due to physiological processes that take place from 2 to 3 days of harvest, which are subsequently followed by microbial decay (Omosuli, *et al.*,2017 ;Beeching, *et al.*,1993). It is, therefore, expedient to process cassava root/tuber soon after harvesting. In a many tropical countries, there is an increasing interest in the development of cassava processing activities (Omosuli, *et al.*,2017). This is because such processing activities are

considered as essential to increasing the economic benefits derivable from fresh cassava root production activities (Omosuli, *et al.*,2017). Interest in the development of cassava processing activities has been intensified since the 2008 food crisis, as it has become necessary to support agricultural processing activities being a strategy toward reducing the reliance of many developing countries on imported staple foods, thereby limiting their exposure to price fluctuations in the international markets and improving national food security (Chapuis, *et al.*,2017). In most sub-Saharan African countries for example, cassava is grown primarily by smallholder farmers and is a significant source of calories for the local population (Chapuis, *et al.*,2017).

The shelf life of cassava is very short, which is associated with the poor technology infrastructure in the region, results in significant postharvest losses (Precoppe, *et al.*,2017). The use of small-scale cassava processing machines could reduce these losses mentioned above (Precoppe, *et al.*,2017). The processing of cassava roots also provides opportunities to add value to raw roots by transforming them into different primary and secondary products of economic significance (Shittu, *et al.*,2016). Starch and flour are the two vital primary products derivable from cassava roots traded globally (Shittu, *et al.*,2016). These two products are dried products often marketed or stored at low moisture levels (10–14%, wet basis) (Shittu, *et al.*,2016).

Globally, several efforts are being made by various institutions, projects, programs, the private sector, and governments to

enhance the quality and utilization of cassava flour, starch and other derivatives (Poku, *et al.*,2018). One of such efforts is the introduction of the flash dryer technology for accelerated production of high-quality cassava flour (HQCF) and high-quality starch (HQS). HQCF is a raw material for the production of glucose syrup, bakery products, and industrial alcohol (Ojide, *et al.*,2022). Flash dryers are state-of-the-art equipment specially designed to rapidly dry semi-processed wet cassava obtained from grating and dewatering of cassava roots/tubers within 3 seconds, into HQCF that is ready for human and commercial use (Chapuis *et al.*, 2018; Africa Innovations Institute., 2018

Sustainable waste management had become a major problem to both developed and developing countries of the World (Ouda *et al.*, 2016). While the developed countries are marginally able to manage the waste menace, it had become a cankerworm to the tropical agrarian countries of Africa usually besieged with non-implementable as well as corrupt manipulation of waste management policies (Ouda *et al.*, 2016; Oghenejoboh *et al.*, 2017). In Nigeria for example, indiscriminate disposal of unsegregated solid wastes into the environment has become the norm (Oghenejoboh *et al.*, 2017). It is common to see heaps of solid wastes dumped in undeveloped plots of land, uncompleted buildings, open fields and water canals/channels (Oghenejoboh, *et al.*, 2017; Babayemi, *et al.*, 2016; Ideriah, *et al.*, 2010). Agricultural waste, especially from cassava production contributes a greater percentage to the total waste generated annually that pose disposal nuisance in Nigeria (Babayemi, *et al.*, 2016).

Processing of cassava into garri is a multi-staged process that has high potential to causes adverse environmental impacts (Nnaji and Akanno, 2022). Sustainability concerns in cassava processing is another major factor of consideration (Nnaji and Akanno, 2022). For example, Cassava processing firms in Africa are mostly of small or medium size; only a few large scale processing industries are in operations which use state-of-the-art flash dryers in South and West Africa (Nnaji and Akanno, 2022). Flash drying equipment, for small-sized enterprises, have low operating costs & capital requirement and simple to build & operate (Nnaji and Akanno, 2022). In Nigeria for example, about 157 cassava processors invested in “first-generation” flash dryers between 2006 and 2016 (Ojide *et al.*,2022). These first-generation flash dryers were those fabricated before the first innovations to improve the efficiency of the heat exchanger. Unfortunately, not a lot of the machines are still in use today due to their low energy efficiency and subsequent high operational costs, (Ojide *et al.*,2022).

Several factors are responsible for the high operational costs and demise/extinction of the cassava processing plants/equipment/factories (Precoppe,, *et al.*, 2020). The primary factor is the high energy cost of fuelling the burner to heat the drying air through a heat exchanger; others include the location of factories in urban centers benefitting from better access to grid electricity, but far from the source of fresh cassava. This often result to high cost of transportation of the raw materials being cassava tubers from farm where they are harvested to the factory for processing. In addition, cassava roots, being perishable within 48 hours after harvest, a lot of losses occur before the roots get to the factory

(Ampah *et al.*, 2017). Delay in receiving enough cassava roots for processing also impedes optimal utilization of the flash dryer (Ampah *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, the need to scale up use of energy-efficient small-scale (3–10 ton product/day) flash dryers in the entire sub-saharan Africa region has become necessary for sustainability and enhanced cassava value chain in the entire sub-region (Chapuis, *et al.*, 2017; Chapuis, *et al.*, 2018).

Cassava being a staple food crop for millions of people around the world, and its processing is a major industry (Otekunrin and Sawicka, 2019). However, traditional cassava processing methods can be environmentally harmful and economically inefficient (Aworh, 2023). In recent years, there has been a growing interest in developing novel sustainable cassava processing practices (Amelework, *et al.*, 2021). One of the most significant challenges in cassava processing is the high volume of water consumption (Amelework, *et al.*, 2021). Meanwhile, the traditional methods of cassava processing require large volumes of water to wash and soak the cassava roots, and much of this water is wasted (Egbune, *et al.*, 2023). New technologies are being developed and emerging to reduce water consumption in cassava processing, such as dry peeling and ultrasonic cleaning of cassava tubers (Pandiselvam, *et al.*, 2022). Another challenge is the disposal of cassava peels, which is a by-product of processing (Rogoski, *et al.*, 2023). Cassava peels contain toxic compounds, and traditional disposal methods can pollute the environment (Malav, *et al.*, 2020). Whereas novel sustainable practices for cassava peel disposal include composting, vermi-composting, and anaerobic digestion

(Jain, *et al.*, 2021). In addition to these environmental benefits, novel sustainable cassava processing practices can also be economically viable. For example, reducing water consumption can save businesses money on their water bills (Feleke, *et al.*, 2021). Composting cassava peel can produce nutrient-rich fertilizer that can be used to grow cassava or other crops (Aso, *et al.*, 2020). Also anaerobic digestion can be used to produce biogas from cassava wastes, which can be used to generate electricity or heat both of which have economic and environmental benefit (Nwuche, *et al.*, 2023). Some specific examples of novelty areas in sustainable cassava processing practices include:

- i. Biogas-powered cassava processing system: Biogas from cassava peels can be used to power cassava processing machines (Nwuche, *et al.*, 2023). This is a closed-loop system that reduces waste and produces renewable energy.
- ii. Solar-powered cassava processing: Solar power can be harnessed and used to power all aspects of cassava processing, from washing and peeling to drying and grinding (Bhat, *et al.*, 2023). This can help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and save businesses money on energy costs.
- iii. Zero-waste cassava processing system: Zero-waste cassava processing is a holistic approach that aims to eliminate all waste from cassava processing process (Cruz, *et al.*, 2023). This is usually achieved by using all parts of cassava plant, including the peel, leaves, and stems, to produce valuable products.

A comparative analysis of the environmental impact and economic viability of novel sustainable cassava

processing practices is still in its early stages (Meramo-Hurtado, *et al.*, 2021). However, there is evidence to suggest that these sustainable practices can be both environmentally beneficial and economically viable. For example, a study by the International Center for Tropical Agriculture (ICAT) found that solar-powered cassava processing can reduce greenhouse gas emissions up to 90%, (Parmar, and Precoppe, 2021). Additionally, a study by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) found that biogas-powered cassava processing can save businesses expenditures up to 50% on their energy costs (Rupf, *et al.*, 2016). While novel sustainable cassava processing practices may require high initial investment, the long-term savings on energy and waste disposal costs can make them economically viable, (Mizik, 2021).. Additionally, governments of many countries offer subsidies and other incentives for businesses that adopt sustainable practices, (Bai, *et al.*, 2022). Continued research and development in this area is needed to further optimize these practices and make them more widely accessible to cassava processors around the world. In the whole of this; cassava products consumers stands to derive better satisfaction from consumption of sustainable cassava products (Kolawole, *et al.*, 2010).

Sustainable food security means enough food for everyone at present plus the ability to provide enough in the future with minimal or no negative impact on the environment (Kolawole, *et al.*, 2010). The global food security is in question today, with ever increasing food prices resulting from adverse climatic effects on

agricultural production, persistent rise in oil prices leading to increased running costs for farm tractors& other machineries, increasing use of food items for other products like bio-ethanol and reduction of government spending on agriculture (Kolawole, *et al.*, 2010). Promoting cassava worldwide as food for both man and animal would not be difficult, but the modern harvesting and processing has some engineering constraints, causing technical, resource, socio-economic and organizational challenges (Nweke, *et al.*, 2002). The market demand for sustainable cassava processing derivatives and products is growing rapidly, driven by a number of factors, including:

- i. Increasing awareness of the environmental and social benefits of sustainable cassava production and processing (Lamboll, *et al.*, 2015). Cassava is a highly drought-tolerant crop that can be grown on marginal land, and its processing can be done in a way that minimizes environmental impact (Mombo, *et al.*, 2017). Additionally, cassava is a good source of carbohydrates and other nutrients, and its processing can create jobs and income opportunities in rural areas (Mombo, *et al.*, 2017).
- ii. Growing demand for gluten-free and other alternative food products. Cassava is a naturally gluten-free ingredient, and it can be used to produce a wide range of food products, including flour, starch, noodles, bread, and pasta (Gao, *et al.*, 2018). This is making cassava increasingly attractive to consumers who are following

gluten-free or other dietary restrictions.

- iii. Rising demand for biofuels and other industrial products derived from cassava. Cassava can be processed to produce ethanol, biodiesel, and other biofuels. It can also be used to produce a variety of industrial products, such as adhesives, textiles, and pharmaceuticals (Nizzy, and Kannan, 2022). This is creating new markets for cassava derivatives and products.

The market for sustainable cassava processing derivatives and products is particularly strong in developing countries, where cassava is a major staple food crop (Anyanwu, *et al.*, 2015). However, demand is also growing in developed countries, as consumers become more aware of the benefits of cassava and its products. Some specific examples of sustainable cassava processing derivatives and products that are in high demand include:

- a. Cassava flour: Cassava flour can be used to make a wide range of gluten-free food products, such as bread, pasta, and cookies. It is also a good source of carbohydrates and other nutrients (Gao, *et al.*, 2018).
- b. Cassava starch: Cassava starch is a versatile ingredient that can be used in a variety of food and industrial products, (Yazid, *et al.*, 2018). Cassava starch is used as a thickener and binder in food products, and it can also be used to produce biofuels and other industrial products.
- c. Cassava noodles: Cassava noodles are a gluten-free alternative to traditional wheat noodles. They are popular in Asia and other parts of the world, and they are becoming

increasingly popular in developed countries as well.

- d. Cassava bread: Cassava bread is a gluten-free alternative to traditional wheat bread, (Fiorda, *et al.*, 2013). Cassava bread is popular in developing countries, and it is becoming increasingly popular in developed countries as well.
- e. Cassava ethanol: Cassava ethanol is a biofuel that can be used to power vehicles and generate electricity (Adelekan, 2017; Dai, *et al.*, 2006). Cassava ethanol is a good alternative to fossil fuels, and it is becoming increasingly important in the transition to a clean energy economy.

The market for sustainable cassava processing derivatives and products is expected to continue to grow in the coming years, as consumers become more aware of the benefits of cassava and its products, (Ilona, *et al.*, 2017). Governments and businesses are also investing in sustainable cassava production and processing, which is further driving the growth of this market. Conclusively, both academic and industrial researchers are also taking advantages of this important global need. The problems (challenges) identified above are knowledge gaps that necessitated this research to close them out. This paper was designed to do the following: to assess the environmental impact of cassava processing plants; to evaluate economic viability of sustainable cassava processing practices; and to compare and analyze the relationship between sustainability and economic viability. The need to address these areas of novelty itemized above by conducting a comparative analysis that combines environmental impact and economic viability occasioned this

research, which can contribute to the development of more sustainable cassava processing practices with broader implications for agricultural and food processing sustainability in the 21st century.

Materials and Method

The materials used include: field note; calculator; engineering design documents of seven models of cassava processing equipment; pen; bill of engineering measurement and evaluation document for the respective models of cassava processing equipment; computer system; and Microsoft excel.

The methodology applied considered seven different models of cassava processing equipment. Each of these designs (models/line) processes cassava into specific derivatives like: Garri (white or oiled/yellow); Cassava starch; Cassava flour and bio-ethanol respectively. The models were designated as: “A”, “B”, “C”, “D”, “E”, “F” and “G”. Cost data were extracted from “the bill of engineering measurement and evaluation (BEME)” of each design being the primary source of data for this research. Analysis of collected data was carried out using payback period method and breakeven point for each model/design/line considered.

Data Collection

The cost data collected for each models are broadly categorized into three main types as follow:

- a. Fixed cost include;
 - Original Purchase cost of model/design/line;
 - Cost of Factory Land;
 - Cost of Construction of Factory Building;
 - Cost of Provision of industrial water borehole, associated pipping

network and storage tanks;

- Cost of Provision of suitable diesel/CNG generator (installation and commissioning of three phase power supply) bearing the required electrical power for all associated equipment;
- Cost of Security surveillance CCTV system;
- Cost of operational Licenses, permits and certifications;
- Cost of Material haulage and handling equipment (including dump trucks, Gator, Tractors with tipping buckets);
- Shipping charge @ 3 % of total equipment cost;
- Customs duty;
- In-country haulage of equipment, including fork lifting and crane lifting during installation; and
- Installation & commissioning, (including training of workers, clients to take up the cost of round trip tickets, working visa, local accommodation and pay salary

b. Variable cost include:

- Purchase of cassava tuber/roots (raw materials)
- Salaries and wages of factory workers
- Fuelling cost
- Overhead cost (office maintenance and other ancillary cost, Vehicle

- maintenance and transportation)
- Miscellaneous Expenditure

c. Expected Revenue/ Returns on Investment from model/design/line.

The expected revenue from sales of one derivative or combination of more than one derivatives the model/design/line. These include:

- Sales of Garri (white or oiled/yellow);
- Sales of Cassava starch;
- Sales of raw Cassava
- Sales of Cassava flour; and
- Sales of **bio**-ethanol respectively.

Data Analysis

Analysis of collected data was carried out using payback period method/scheme and breakeven point for each model/design/line considered. It is noteworthy that for the purpose of this economic analysis; 1\$ = ₦920.

Payback period

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total cost} &= \text{fixed cost} + (\text{variable cost} \times 12) \\ &= 913,406,000 + (274,517,702 \times 12) \\ &= 913,406,000 + 3,294,212,424 \end{aligned}$$

Total cost = 4,207,618,424

Expected yearly Revenue/ Returns on Investment from model “A” = 4,123,600,000

The feasibility analysis was done using payback period (PBP) as follows:

$$\text{PBP} = \frac{\text{Initial investment Cost}}{\text{Cash Inflow}} \text{Eqn. 1}$$

$$\text{PBP} = \frac{4,207,618,424}{4,123,600,000}$$

1.02 = 12 months

Therefore, the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “A” is one year (12 months).

The procedure stated in 3.1.1 was repeated and applied to models; B”, “C”, “D”, “E”, “F” and “G” to determine their payback period as presented in Table 4.

The Breakeven Point for Model “A” the Cassava Processing Factory

The breakeven point for cassava the processing venture is the point where the total revenue generated from the sales of cassava products is equal to the total costs incurred in producing and selling those products. In this regard, the breakeven point will be computed for each model of cassava processing equipment used for the research. To calculate the breakeven point, we need to know the following in each case:

- i. The fixed costs: These are the costs that are incurred regardless of the level of production, such as rent, salaries, and utilities.
- ii. The variable costs: These are the costs that vary directly with the level of production, such as the cost of cassava being the raw material, labor, and packaging.
- iii. The selling price per unit of cassava product/derivative.

The breakeven point for using model “A” to produce Cassava flour can be calculated using the following formula:
Breakeven point = Fixed costs / (Selling price per unit - Variable cost per unit) Eqn. 2

The following information for cassava processing for model “A: was determined in 4.4.1 as follows:

- i. Fixed costs = ₦ 913,406,000
- ii. Variable costs per unit = 274,517,702 / 780,000 = ₦ 352
- iii. Selling price per unit = 4,123,600,000 ÷ 780,000 = ₦ 5,287

Contribution margin = Selling price per unit - Variable costs per unit
Contribution margin = 5,287 - 352 =

4,935. Hence, the breakeven point is calculated by apply equation 2. as follows:

Breakeven point = $913,406,000 \div (5,287 - 352) = 913,406,000 \div 4,935 = 185,087$ units.

This means that if model “A” is adopted’ the factory must sell 185,087 units of cassava products in order to recover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 185,087 units, it will make a profit. If it sells less than 185,087 units, it will make a loss.

Similarly, the procedure sated in 3.1.2 was repeated and applied to other models (“B”, “ C”, “ D”, “ E”, “ F” and “ G”) to their break even points as presented in Table 4.

Results and Discussion

Results

The results obtained the analysis are presented in tables 1 to 4 as follows:

Table 1. Fixed cost for Model “A”

S/N	Items	Quantity	Total ₦
1	Cassava Flour and Ethanol Combined Line (100T/D fresh cassava, 20T cassava flour and 6T ethanol with 96.4%.)	1 set	750,720,000
2	Factory Land	1½Hectare	1,500,000
3	Construction of Factory Building (About 42m×12½m×6m Length × Width × Height)	-	65,000,000
4	Provision of industrial water borehole, associated pipping network and storage tanks	1 set	3,000,000
5	Provision of 200 KVA diesel/CNG generator (installation and commissioning) with a three phase power supply	1 set	34,650,000.00
6	Security surveillance CCTV system	1 set	1,000,000
7	Licenses, permits and certifications		1,000,000
8	Material haulage and handling equipment (including dump trucks, Gator, Tractors with tipping buckets)		5,000,000
9	Shipping charge @ 3 % of total equipment cost	-	22,521,600
10	Customs duty (being farm/Agric./Food production Equipment ought to be duty free but lets assume a worst case scenario of 1% of total equipment cost)	-	7,507,200
11	In-country haulage including fork lifting and crane lifting during installation	-	7,507,200
12	Installation & commissioning, (including training of workers, clients should take charge of round trip tickets, working visa, local accommodation and pay salary one person \$100 per day),	2 persons x 30 days	14,000,000

Table 2: Variable cost for Model “A”:

S/N	Variable cost	Price per Unit (₦)	Monthly Total (₦)
1.	Purchase of case tuber (100T/D)	3000T/M @ ₦75,000	225,000,000
2.	Salaries and wages of Factory workers	22 person @ ₦60,000 monthly Per worker	1,320,000
3.	Fuelling cost (54.72 litre per hour)	₦842.250 per litre	33,183,302.4
4.	Overhead cost (office maintenance and other ancillary cost, Vehicle maintenance and transportation) @ 1% of total equipment cost	7,507,200	7,507,200
5.	miscellaneous Expenditure @ 1% of total equipment cost	7,507,200	7,507,200
Total			
			274,517,702

Table 3: Expected Revenue/ Returns on Investment from Model “A”

S/N	Source of Returns on Investment	Price per Unit (₦)	Monthly Total ₦	Yearly Total ₦
1.	Sales of cassava flour	(20T/D) @ ₦340,000 per tonne	204,000,000	2,482,000,000
2.	Sales of ethanol	(6T/D ethanol with 96.4%) @ ₦760,000	136,800,000	1,641,600,000
Total				
4,123,600,000				

Table 4: Results of payback period (PBP) and Breakeven Points for the different cassava processing machine Model/Design/line

Model	Payback Period (months/years)	Breakeven Point (units)
“A”	$PBP = \frac{4,207,618,424}{4,123,600,000} = 1.02 = 12 \text{ months}$	Breakeven point = 913,406,000 ÷ 4,935 = 185,087 units
“B”	(i) If yellow garri is to be produced using model “B”, $PBP = \frac{1,850,422,360}{2,090,880,000} = 0.88 = 11 \text{ months}$ (ii) If white garri is to be produced using model “B”, $PBP = \frac{1,845,422,360}{1,615,680,000} = 1.14 = 14 \text{ months}$	Breakeven point = 292,040,000 ÷ 4353 = 67,089 units
“C”	$PBP = \frac{3,529,724,028}{3,525,120,000} = 1.001 = 12 \text{ months}$	Breakeven point = 439,430,000 ÷ 3,782 = 116,189 units
“D”	$PBP = \frac{4,902,794,480}{3,378,240,000} = 1.4 = 17 \text{ months}$	Breakeven point = 361,699,540 ÷ 3,644 = 154,336 units
“E”	$BP = \frac{3,088,014,620}{1,468,800,000} = 2.1 = 25 \text{ months}$	Breakeven point = 234,312,260 ÷ 3,419 = 68,532 units
“F”	(i) If yellow garri is to be produced using model “F” $PBP = \frac{1,794,384,360}{2,090,880,000} = 0.86 = 10 \text{ months}$ (ii) If white garri is to be produced using model “F” $PBP = \frac{1,789,384,360}{1,615,680,000} = 1.1 = 13 \text{ month}$	Breakeven point = 243,730,000 ÷ 4,355 = 55,966 units

“G”	(i) If yellow garri is to be produced using model “G”	Breakeven point = 243,730,000 ÷ 4,237 = 57,524 units
	$\text{PBP} = \frac{517,215,056}{475,200,000} = 1.08 = 13 \text{ months.}$	
	(ii) If white garri is to be produced using model “G”	
	$\text{PBP} = \frac{512,215,056}{367,200,000} = 1.4 = 16 \text{ months.}$	

Discussion

The estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “A” is one year (12 months). While, the Breakeven point for model “A” is 185,087 units. The implication of this is that; if model “A” is adopted, the factory must sell 185,087 units of cassava products in order to cover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 185,087 units, it will make a profit. But if it sells less than 185,087 units, it will make a loss.

For model “B”: If yellow (oiled) garri is to be produced using model “B”, the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “B” is less than one year (11 months). Whereas in the event of using model “B” to produce white garri the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment will be 14 months. The breakeven point for model “B” is 67,089 units. This implies that; if model “B” is selected, the factory must sell 67,089 units of cassava products in order to cover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 67,089 units, it will make a profit. If it sells less than 67,089 units, it will make a loss.

For model “C”: the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “C” is one year (12 months) and breakeven point of 116,189 units. This means that if model “C” is adopted, the factory must sell 116,189 units of cassava products in order to cover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 116,189 units, it

will make a profit. If it sells less than 116,189 units, it will make a loss.

For model “D”: the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “D” is one year plus five months (17 months). Model “D” has a breakeven point of 154,336 units. This means that if model “D” is adopted, the factory must sell 154,336 units of cassava products in order to cover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 154,336 units, it will make a profit. If it sells less than 154,336 units, it will make a loss.

Model “E” has an the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “E” is Two years plus One month (25 months) and a breakeven point of 68,532 units. This means that if model “E” is adopted, the factory must sell 68,532 units of cassava products in order to cover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 68,532 units, it will make a profit. However, if it sells less than 68,532 units, it will make a loss.

For model “F”: If yellow garri is to be produced using model “F”, the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “F” is less than one year (10 months). Whereas in the event of using model “F” to produce white garri the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment will be 13 months (one year plus two months). This means that if model “F” is adopted, the factory must sell 55,966 units of cassava products in order to cover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 55,966 units, it will make a profit.

Meanwhile, if it sells less than 55,966 units, it will make a loss.

For model “G”: If yellow garri is to be produced using model “G”, the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment on model “G” is one year plus one month (13 months). Whereas in the event of using model “G” to produce white garri the estimated time to recover initial capital of investment will be One year plus Five months (16 months). Model “G” has a breakeven point of 57,524. This means that if model “G” is adopted, the factory must sell 57,524 units of cassava products in order to cover its total costs. If the factory sells more than 57,524 units, it will make a profit. And lastly, if the factory sells less than 57,524 units, it will make a loss.

Conclusion

A comprehensive study was carried-out to demystify the technical and financial requirements for the establishment of sustainable and profitable cassava processing business aimed at converting raw cassava tubers into derivatives like: Garri (white or oiled/yellow); Cassava starch; Cassava flour and bio-ethanol respectively. A potential investor may decide to concentrate on producing a single or combination of derivatives listed in section 2.3, from results of the analyzed data in 3.1.1 and 3.1.2 the following conclusion were made:

1. Model “A” is a cassava flour and ethanol combined line (100T/D fresh cassava, 20T cassava flour and 6T ethanol with 96.4 %.) This model has a payback period (PBP) of one year (12 months). In addition, model “A” has a breakeven point of 185,087 units.
2. Model “B” is a cassava-garri production line (2 tons of cassava tuber per hour = 48 T/D),500-600kg/hr garri output. If

this model is used to process yellow garri it will have a payback period of less than one year (11 months). While if the same model is used to process white garri it will have a payback period of One year plus two month (14 months). In addition, model “B” has a breakeven point of 67,089 units.

3. Model “C”: is a Cassava flour processing line (4TPH cassava raw material into 1 to 1.3 TPH cassava flour output). This model has a payback period (PBP) of one year (12 months and a breakeven point of 116,189 units.
4. Model “D” is a 5TPH Cassava Tuber to Starch processing Line (5TPH cassava tuber input to give 1.25T/H starch output). The model has a payback period (PBP) of one year plus five months (17 months) and a breakeven point of 154,336 units.
5. Model “E”: is a Cassava starch processing line of 12 Tons/day capacity, cassava starch processing line (4 tons/hour of raw cassava to 0.5 tons/hour starch). The model has a payback period (PBP) of two years plus one month (25 months). In addition, model “E” has a breakeven point of 68,532 Units.
6. Model “F” is a garri processing line (2T/H input garri processing line) (2 tons of cassava tuber per hour = 48 T/D)500-600kg/HR garri output; (13.2 T/day). The model has a payback period (PBP less than One year (10 months) when it is to be used to process yellow garri. While the same model when used to process white garri has a payback period (PBP) of One year plus one month (13 months). In addition,

model “F” has a breakeven point of 55,966units.

7. Model “G” is a garri processing line (for 1T/D output garri project). When this model is used to process yellow garri it has a payback period (PBP) of one year plus three months (15 months). While if the same model is used to process white garri, it will have a payback period (PBP) of One year plus Five months (17 months). In addition, model G” has a breakeven point of 57,524 units. A critical look at Models “F” and “G” show that it is more profitable to produce red (oiled) garri using these models because in both cases yellow garri gave shorter time of recovery of investments (payback period).

The payback period of an investment is the period of time during an investor expects to recover his capital spent on establishing a particular business. The general rule of thumb for business feasibility assessment considers business models with less than three years capital recovery period (payback period) to be viable. In this regard; a potential investor might select one or more models from the seven models considered sections 3.1 of this paper as it suits the Investors’ business objective. The decision as to which model (s) to select shall be taken by a potential Investor (s) after due considerations of all the factors/requirements and conditions discussed in this paper. Conclusively; however, in all seven models considered for the research model “F” proved to have the shortest recovery period of ten months when

used to process/produce red (oiled) garri and breakeven point 55,966 units which makes it more attractive to potential investor (s) in cassava processing business venture. Based upon the findings of this paper, the authors propose the following recommendations:

- (1) Provision of access road to the factory location/site to ease material haulage;
- (2) Provision of security/surveillance cameras at strategic points within the factory premises and geo-fencing of the factory boundaries to check unwanted movement of persons, material theft and pilferage;
- (3) An Enterprise Resource Management software should be procured and customized to take stock of all the factory’s activities including: finances/accounting, material requisition, daily operations, stock management, sales, energy use, raw materials needs and management, labour use. This is to completely eliminate fraud and ensure optimum use of resource in the business of cassava processing;
- (4) There is need to convert the outmost black skin of cassava tubers which are termed waste hitherto into animal feed and ethanol, to minimize negative environmental impact by the proposed factory operations and provide additional source of income for the business as well enhanced sustainability status; and
- (5) The factory requires constant power supply with no blackout so as to prevent interruptions of production and downtime. In this regards, diesel or gas generator can be provided to combine with Solar & inverter charging systems to guaranty steady power supply to the factory.
- (6) Continuous staff training and careful implementation of preventive maintenance program/scheme is recommended.

References

- Adelekan, B. A. (2010). Investigation of ethanol productivity of cassava crop as a sustainable source of biofuel in tropical countries. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 9(35).
- Africa Innovations Institute [AfrII] (2018). *Flash Dryer technology eases commercial cassava processing in Northern Uganda*. Available online at: <https://www.afrii.org/flash-dryer-technology-eases-commercial-cassava-processing-in-northern-uganda/> (accessed October 12, 2020).
- Akinola, O. A., Akeredolu, O. A., Azeez, A. A., Adetunji, A. S., & Ojokunle, A. M. (2020). Awareness of cassava farmers on the use of agrochemicals and the adverse effects associated with them in Odigbo Local Government Area of Ondo State. *Journal of Research in Forestry, Wildlife and Environment*, 12(3), 122-131.
- Amelework, A. B., Bairu, M. W., Maema, O., Venter, S. L., & Laing, M. (2021). Adoption and promotion of resilient crops for climate risk mitigation and import substitution: A case analysis of cassava for South African agriculture. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5, 617783.
- Ampah, J., Dziedzoave, N., Agblo, E. T., Bempong, O., Djokoto, F., Addo, I., et al. (2017). *Assessment of a 6-Cyclone Flash Dryer: Technical Report*. "Council for Scientific and Industrial Research - Food Research Institute (CSRI-FRI), ACCRA – GHANA.
- Anyanwu, C. N., Ibeto, C. N., Ezeoha, S. L., & Ogbuagu, N. J. (2015). Sustainability of cassava (*Manihotesculenta* Crantz) as industrial feedstock, energy and food crop in Nigeria. *Renewable Energy*, 81, 745-752.
- Asante, E. (2022). *Environmentally sustainable cassava processing in Ghana: Trade-offs between the different United Nations Sustainable Development Goals* (Doctoral dissertation).
- Aso, S. N. (2020). Digestate: the coproduct of biofuel production in a circular economy, and new results for cassava peeling residue digestate. *Renewable energy-technologies and applications*. Available on : <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0956713522005862>.
- Aworh, O. C. (2023). African traditional foods and sustainable food security. *Food Control*, 109393. Volume 145, 2023, 109393. ISSN 0956-7135, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodcont.2022.109393>.
- Babayemi, J.O., Dauda, K.T., (2009). Evaluation of solid waste generation, categories and disposal options in developing countries: a case study of Nigeria. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manag.* 13, 83–84. doi: 10.4314/jasem.v13i3.55370.
- Bai, X., Wang, K. T., Tran, T. K., Sadiq, M., Trung, L. M., & Khudoykulov, K. (2022). Measuring China's green economic recovery and energy environment sustainability: econometric analysis of sustainable development goals. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 75, 768-779.
- Bayata, A. (2019). Review on nutritional value of cassava for use as a staple food. *Sci J Anal Chem*, 7(4), 83-91.
- Beeching, J. R., Marmey, P., Gavaldà, M. C., Noirot, M., Haysom, H. R., Hughes,

- M. A., et al. (1993). An Assessment of genetic diversity within a collection of cassava (*manihotesculentacrantz*) germplasm using molecular markers. *Annal Bot.* 72, 515–520. doi: 10.1006/anbo.1993.1139.
- Bhat, S. A., Kumar, V., Kumar, S., Atabani, A. E., Badruddin, I. A., &Chae, K. J. (2023). Supercapacitors production from waste: A new window for sustainable energy and waste management. *Fuel*, 337, 127125.
- Chapuis, A., Precoppe, M., Méot, J. M., Sriroth, K., and Tran, T. (2017). Pneumatic drying of cassava starch: Numerical analysis and guidelines for the design of efficient small-scale dryers. *Dry. Technol.* 35, 393–408, doi: 10.1080/07373937.2016.1177537.
- Chapuis, A., Tran, T., Giraldo, F., Moreno, M., Precoppe, M., Moreno, J., et al. (2018). Development and trials of a small-capacity pilot flash dryer for cassava-derived products. A presentation made during Triennial symposium of International Society for Tropical Crops in Cali, Colombia. 22-25 October 2018.
- Costa, R. C., Ramos, M. D. N., Fleck, L., Gomes, S. D., & Aguiar, A. (2022). Critical analysis and predictive models using the physicochemical characteristics of cassava processing wastewater generated in Brazil. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, 47, 102629.
- Cruz, I. A., Andrade, L. R. S., Bharagava, R. N., Nadda, A. K., Bilal, M., Figueiredo, R. T., & Ferreira, L. F. R. (2021). Valorization of cassava residues for biogas production in Brazil based on the circular economy: An updated and comprehensive review. *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, 4, 100196.
- Dai, D., Hu, Z., Pu, G., Li, H., & Wang, C. (2006). Energy efficiency and potentials of cassava fuel ethanol in Guangxi region of China. *Energy conversion and management*, 47(13-14), 1686-1699.
- De Jesus, M. A. S., Aguiar Dutra, A. R. D., Cirani, C. B. S., Jesus, K. R. E., Neto, R. C. S., & Guerra, J. B. A. (2022). Eco-innovation assessment of biodigesters technology: an application in cassava processing industries in the south of Brazil, Parana state. *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy*, 1-18.
- Droppelmann, K., Günther, P., Kamm, F., Rippke, U., Voigt, C., &Walenda, B. (2018). *Cassava, the 21st century crop for smallholders?. Exploring innovations along the livelihood value chain nexus in Malawi*”. Centre for Rural Development (SLE) Berlin, SLE Publication Series (2018): S 274.Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin.
- Egbune, E. O., Ezedom, T., Orororo, O. C., Egbune, O. U., Avwioroko, O. J., Aganbi, E., ...&Tonukari, N. J. (2023). Solid-state fermentation of cassava (*ManihotesculentaCrantz*): a review. *World Journal of Microbiology and Biotechnology*, 39(10), 259.
- Feleke, S., Cole, S. M., Sekabira, H., Djouaka, R., &Manyong, V. (2021). Circular bioeconomy research for development in sub-Saharan Africa: innovations, gaps, and actions. *Sustainability*, 13(4), 1926.
- Fiorda, F. A., Soares Jr, M. S., da Silva, F. A., Grosman, M. V., &Souto, L. R.

- (2013). Microstructure, texture and colour of gluten-free pasta made with amaranth flour, cassava starch and cassava bagasse. *LWT-Food Science and Technology*, 54(1), 132- 138.
- Gao, Y., Janes, M. E., Chaiya, B., Brennan, M. A., Brennan, C. S., & Prinyawiwatkul, W. (2018). Gluten-free bakery and pasta products: prevalence and quality improvement. *International Journal of Food Science & Technology*, 53(1), 19-32.
https://gala.gre.ac.uk/id/eprint/35067/7/35067_PRECOPPE_Solar_technology_casts_a_bright_future_for_improved_cassava.pdf.
- Ideriah, T.J.K., Harry, F.O., Stanley, H.O., Igbara, J.K., 2010. Heavy metals contamination of soils and vegetation around solid waste dump in Port-Harcourt, Nigeria. *J. Appl. Sci. Environ. Manag.* 14 (1), 101– 103.
doi: 10.4314/jasem.v14i1.56511.
- Iloa, P., Bouis, H. E., Palenberg, M., Moursi, M., & Oparinde, A. (2017). Vitamin A cassava in Nigeria: crop development and delivery. *African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development*, 17(2), 12000-12025.
- Jain, R., Pattanaik, L., Padhi, S. K., & Naik, S. N. (2021). Role of Microbes and Microbial Consortium in Solid Waste Management. *Environmental and Agricultural Microbiology: Applications for Sustainability*, 383-422.
- Kolawole P.O., Agbetoye L. and Simeon A.O., (2010) Sustaining World Food Security with Improved Cassava Processing Technology: The Nigeria Experience. *Journal of Sustainability*. *Sustainability* 2010, 2(12), 3681-3694; <https://doi.org/10.3390/su2123681>.
www.mdpi.com/journal/sustainability.
- Kouassi, J. L., Gyau, A., Diby, L., Bene, Y., & Kouamé, C. (2021). Assessing land use and land cover change and farmers' perceptions of deforestation and land degradation in South-West Côte d'Ivoire, West Africa. *Land*, 10(4), 429.
- Lamboll, R., Nelson, V., Posthumus, H., Martin, A., Adebayo, K., Alacho, F., & Westby, A. (2015). Practical lessons on scaling up smallholder-inclusive and sustainable cassava value chains in Africa. *Food Chain*, 5(1-2), 28-52.
- Malav, L. C., Yadav, K. K., Gupta, N., Kumar, S., Sharma, G. K., Krishnan, S., & Bach, Q. V. (2020). A review on municipal solid waste as a renewable source for waste-to-energy project in India: Current practices, challenges, and future opportunities. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 277, 123227.
- Meramo-Hurtado, S. I., González-Delgado, Á., Rehmann, L., Quinones-Bolanos, E., & Mehvar, M. (2021). Comparative analysis of biorefinery designs based on acetone-butanol-ethanol fermentation under exergetic, techno-economic, and sensitivity analyses towards a sustainability perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 298, 126761.
- Methil, A., Agrawal, H., & Kaushik, V. (2021, July). One-vs-all methodology based cassava leaf disease detection. In *2021 12th International Conference on Computing*

- Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT)* (pp. 1-7). IEEE.
- Mizik, T. (2021). Economic aspects and sustainability of ethanol production—a systematic literature review. *Energies*, 14(19), 6137.
- Mombo, S., Dumat, C., Shahid, M., & Schreck, E. (2017). A socio-scientific analysis of the environmental and health benefits as well as potential risks of cassava production and consumption. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 24, 5207-5221.
- Nizzy, A. M., & Kannan, S. (2022). A review on the conversion of cassava wastes into value-added products towards a sustainable environment. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(46), 69223-69240.
- Nnaji, C. C., & Akanno, C. C. (2022). Assessment of environmental degradation due to processing of cassava into Garri flakes using pollution indices. *Environmental Processes*, 9(3), 46.
- Nweke, F.I.; Spencer, D.S.C.; Lynam, J.K.(2002)*The Cassava Transformation: Africa's Best Kept Secret*; Michigan State University: East Lansing, MI, USA, 2002; p. 273.
- Nwuche, C. O., Gupta, S., Akor, J., Nweze, J. E., Nweze, J. A., & Unah, V. U. (2023). Biogas from Manure: The Future of Renewable Natural Gas and Its Implications. In *Climate Changes Mitigation and Sustainable Bioenergy Harvest Through Animal Waste: Sustainable Environmental Implications of Animal Waste* (pp. 171-214). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
- Oghenejoboh, K.M., Igbagara, P.W., Oghenejoboh, U.M., (2017). Contamination of agricultural soils by selected heavy metals from municipal solid waste dumpsites—a case study of Oleh town in Nigeria's Niger Delta. *Nigerian J. Technol. Res.* 12 (2), 1–7.
- Ojide, M. G., Adegbite, S., Tran, T., Taborda, L. A., Chapuis, A., Lukombo, S., & Abass, A. (2022). Processors' experience in the use of flash dryer for Cassava-derived products in Nigeria. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 5, 771639.
- Omosuli SV, Ikujenlola AV, Abisuwa AT (2017) Quality assessment of stored fresh Cassava Roots and 'fufu' flour produced from stored roots. *J Food SciNutrThe* 3(1): 009-013.
- Otekunrin, O. A., & Sawicka, B. (2019). Cassava, a 21st century staple crop: How can Nigeria harness its enormous trade potentials. *Acta Scientific Agriculture*, 3(8), 194-202.
- Ouda, O.K.M., Raza, S.A., Nizami, A.S., Reha, M., (2016). Waste to energy potential: a case study of Saudi Arabia. *Renew Sust. Energ. Rev.* 61, 328–340. doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2016.04.005.
- Oyewole, A. L., Ibrahim, F. M., Abegunrin, O. O., Gbadebo, O. V., & Anifowose, T. O. (2022) ANALYSES of Agricultural Waste Disposal Among Cassava Processors In Afijio Local Government Of Oyo State. *Journal of*

- Forestry Research and Management. Vol. 19(4).40-50; 2022, ISSN 0189-8418. Available on: www.jfrm.org.ng.
- Pandiselvam, R., Aydar, A. Y., Kutlu, N., Aslam, R., Sahni, P., Mitharwal, S., & Kothakota, A. (2022). Individual and interactive effect of ultrasound pre-treatment on drying kinetics and biochemical qualities of food: A critical review. *Ultrasonics Sonochemistry*, 106261.
- Parmar, A., & Precoppe, M. (2021). Solar technology casts a bright future for improved cassava processing.
- Pasqualone, A., Caponio, F., Summo, C., Paradiso, V. M., Bottega, G., & Pagani, M. A. (2010). Gluten-free bread making trials from cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) flour and sensory evaluation of the final product. *International Journal of food properties*, 13(3), 562-573.
- Poku, A. G., Birner, R., & Gupta, S. (2018). Is Africa ready to develop a competitive bioeconomy? The case of the cassava value web in Ghana. *Journal of cleaner production*, 200, 134-147.
- Precoppe, M., Chapuis, A., Müller, J., and Abass, A. (2017). Tunnel dryer and pneumatic dryer performance evaluation to improve small-scale cassava processing in Tanzania. *J. Food Process Eng.* 40, e12274. doi: 10.1111/jfpe.12274.
- Precoppe, M., Komlaga, G. A., Chapuis, A., and Müller, J. (2020). Comparative study between current practices on cassava drying by small-size enterprises in Africa. *Appl. Sci.* 10, 1–17. doi: 10.3390/app10217863.
- Rogoski, W., Pereira, G. N., Cesca, K., de Oliveira, D., & de Andrade, C. J. (2023). An Overview on Pretreatments for the Production of Cassava Peels-based Xyloligosaccharides: State of Art and Challenges. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*, 1-17.
- Rupf, G. V., Bahri, P. A., de Boer, K., & McHenry, M. P. (2016). Broadening the potential of biogas in Sub-Saharan Africa: An assessment of feasible technologies and feedstocks. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 61, 556-571.
- Seweya, L. N., Chacha, N. T., & Saitoti, J. (2023). Briquette quality assessment from corn husk, bagasse, and cassava roots using banana peels, wastepaper, and clay soil as binders. *Environmental Quality Management*.
- Shittu, T. A., Alimi, B. A., Wahab, B., Sanni, L. O., and Abass, A. B. (2016). Cassava Flour and Starch: "Processing Technology and Utilization" in *Tropical Roots and Tubers: Production, Processing and Technology*, First Edition., eds Sharma H. K., Njintang N. Y., Singhal R. S. and Kaushal P. New York, NY: John Wiley and Sons, Ltd.
- Tran, T., Abass, A., Andrade, L. A. T., Chapuis, A., Precoppe, M., Adinsi, L., & Dufour, D. (2022). Cost-effective cassava processing: Case study of small-scale flash-dryer reengineering. In *Root, Tuber and Banana Food System Innovations: Value Creation for Inclusive*

Outcomes (pp. 105-143). Cham:
Springer International Publishing.

Yazid, N. S. M., Abdullah, N.,
Muhammad, N., &
Matias-Peralta, H. M. (2018).
Application of starch and starch-
based products in food
industry. *Journal of Science and
Technology*, 10(2).